

A Voice for Freedom:

Jazz History and the African American Struggle

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Abstract

The history of jazz is inseparable from the struggles and triumphs of African Americans, reflecting the complex intersections of music, culture, and politics. Born in the American South, jazz emerged as a fusion of African and European musical traditions, shaped by the legacy of slavery and the pursuit of freedom. The genre became both a product of and a response to systemic racism, with its development paralleling the Great Migration and the civil rights movement. Jazz artists not only revolutionized music but also used their craft to protest segregation, inequality, and discrimination. Songs like Billie Holiday's "Strange Fruit" and Charles Mingus's "Fables of Faubus" provided poignant critiques of injustice, while figures like Louis Armstrong, Duke Ellington, and John Coltrane pushed boundaries through activism and artistry. Despite facing societal and industry barriers, jazz musicians helped dismantle racial divides, inspiring cultural progression and offering a legacy of resistance and innovation.

Introduction

The history of jazz is inextricably linked to the struggles and resilience of African Americans in the United States. Emerging alongside the transformation of African Americans' legal and political status following the abolition of slavery, jazz reflects the complexities of a newly defined freedom.¹ While emancipation granted certain rights, it failed to address the deep-rooted demographic and economic disparities faced by Black citizens.² By the early 20th century, approximately 90% of African Americans still lived in the South, their conditions largely unchanged from decades earlier.³ As such, the birth of jazz in the South was not only inevitable but also a powerful testament to the enduring cultural creativity of African Americans in the face of systemic oppression.⁴

Black Culture in a White Society

During the later nineteenth century, New Orleans was the only place in the U.S. that allowed enslaved people to own drums. Thus, the traditions of West Africans remained intact in the South and subsequently merged into European classical music and the church hymns of enslaved Black people, including the incorporation of Afro-Cuban rhythms, which began the development of jazz.⁵ Given the new-found freedom after slavery's abolition, African Americans became working musicians as part of the entertainment industry – one of which, Scott Joplin, developed the ragtime genre, the precursor of jazz;⁶ musicians and bands attempting to imitate ragtime using improvisation popularized the genre into the industry as early jazz musicians such as George Vital Laine performed throughout New Orleans.⁷ During this time, the terms 'jazz' and 'ragtime' were nearly synonymous and used interchangeably due to ragtime's influence on early jazz.⁸ While this early form of jazz was popular in New Orleans due to imitative musicians, its popularity flourished in Missouri, where Scott Joplin lived at the end of the nineteenth century –

subsequently, after his move to St. Louis at the beginning of the twentieth century, the number of ragtime composers in the city grew exponentially, and Joplin's performance at the Chicago World's Fair in 1893 led to the craze of the genre in the Northern U.S.⁹ Likewise, modern jazz developed in New Orleans, gaining notoriety around 1917.¹⁰

Given the economic and societal conditions in the South in the early twentieth century, the Great Migration, a massive movement of African Americans out of the South, comes as no surprise. Hence, the migration of culture and Southern influences to the North, especially music, is equally expected.¹¹ The movement of rural culture into the cities due to urbanization also helps explain the quick spread of jazz across the nation, alongside the greater access to employment opportunities and increased capital gains.¹² Benny Goodman also assisted in the integration of these cultures, being the first white bandleader to hire a black musician into his ensemble in 1936 – Teddy Wilson – hiring Lionel Hampton as well the following year.¹³ For the following years, jazz remained the primary form of popular dance music in the nation, lasting from approximately 1915 until 1955.¹⁴

The Role of Jazz in Civil Rights

While jazz developed under the roots of black ethnic struggles, many songs of the time were reflective or protestive against political issues that were derogative toward African Americans, including segregation.¹⁵ Verity discusses one particularly significant song relevant to black civil rights:

Billie Holiday incorporated the song "Strange Fruit" into her set list in 1939. Adapted from a poem by a New York high school teacher, "Strange Fruit" was inspired by the 1930 lynching of two Blacks, Thomas Shipp, and Abram Smith. It juxtaposes the horrid image of Black bodies hanging from trees with a description of the idyllic South. Holiday delivered the song night after night, often overwhelmed by emotion, causing it to become an anthem of early civil rights movements.¹⁶

This proved to demonstrate the role of jazz music and its function in the civil rights movement – providing a voice for African Americans, drawing greater attention to racial issues and discrimination throughout the nation, and expressing support for and promoting various Civil Rights organizations.¹⁷

Jazz artists were not without discrimination and faced issues in finding shelter, food, toilet facilities, and many other basic needs when on tour.¹⁸ Many were banned from hotels near tour locations, disallowed from participation in live radio broadcasts, and decreased record sales. Nonetheless, the goal of raising awareness of the issues and promoting freedom continued as the artists continued to incorporate these issues and discussions of inequality within their music.¹⁹

According to Gammage:

Jazz musicians of color faced great discrimination in their own industry. These practices, such as the cabaret card and other tactics of police brutality, inevitably shaped the lives of these musicians and the music they created; ironically Jim Crow had ultimately helped to fabricate the genre and its audiences^[3]. Jazz audiences, originally comprising of exclusively African-Americans and moving into more interracial territory over the course of the 20th century, could not ignore the racialized aspect of the music.²⁰

As well, these issues were exemplified due to the nature of segregation at the times, as many basic necessities like hotels and restaurants were inaccessible due to being separated into “White Only” establishments.²¹

Jazz and Cultural Progression

As many popular jazz artists continued their support for activist groups and protest against racial issues explicitly through their music, some artists like Louis Armstrong, who performed primarily for white audiences, intentionally continued this trend through implicit and ironic lyrics and intentional stereotyping, much like Langston Hughes’ poem “Harlem” which serves the same purpose – as can be seen in Armstrong’s “(What Did I Do To Be So) Black and Blue?” especially.²² Commentary – which was seen as risky, weighty, and out of context of the shows – became

Armstrong's means of promoting social justice, as well as revolting against performing in locations due to black civilians being treated poorly, going so far as to cancel a tour to the Soviet Union after witnessing the Little Rock Crisis in 1957.²³ Artist Charles Mingus also responded to this event in his composition "Fables of Faubus" which features lyrics that explicitly represented harsh critiques of Jim Crow attitudes – some of the most bitter seen throughout all of jazz activism.²⁴

Similarly, artist Duke Ellington was also subtle in his dealing with prejudice – renting multiple train cars for his band to travel, eat, and sleep, never playing for segregated audiences, and writing music that sought to celebrate black identity and convey his view of jazz as "African-American classical music" such as "Black, Brown, and Beige" and "Jump for Joy" – intentionally finding loopholes to avoid the Jim Crow laws and imposing respect for his music.²⁵ Max Roach, another activist often outspoken, wrote songs of similar intention and music which reflected upon the heightened civil rights movement protests in the 1960s.²⁶ As well, artist John Coltrane was known primarily for performing benefit concerts and writing numerous songs in support of Dr. Martin Luther King and the civil rights movement – seen particularly in the highly political song "Alabama" based on King's speech at the memorial service following the Birmingham bombing.²⁷

Dominant Culture in the Jazz World

Dominant culture can be seen in jazz not only in language and behavior as a result of segregation, but racial discrimination against jazz artists was seen throughout the world – jazz music was condemned by the Nazis, considered sensationalized 'worker music' and bourgeois art by the Soviets, and considered low-class even within the United States.²⁸ Many listeners were impatient with jazz music due to its musical theory complexity and, thus, difficult to appreciate, and growth within casual and musically untrained audiences was stagnant and suffered in popular

audiences early on.²⁹ These issues were not only seen in jazz, but African American musicians in general, according to Gioia:

[The] most forceful creative currents in this society came from the African-American underclass. Should this surprise us? The musician's "special" role as slave or lunatic, outsider or pariah, has a long tradition dating back to ancient times. As recently as the twentieth century, some cultures retained religious prohibitions asserting the "uncleanliness" of believers eating at the same table as musicians. Yet the role of slave labor in the production of African-American song makes for an especially sad chapter in this melancholy history. [...] In other locales, African elements in the slaves' music were discouraged or explicitly suppressed. During the Stono Rebellion of 1739, drums had been used to signal an attack on the white population. Anxious to prevent further uprisings, South Carolina banned any use of drums by slaves. The Georgia slave code went even further in prohibiting not only drums, but also horns or loud instruments. Religious organizations also participated in the attempt to control the African elements of the slaves' music. The Hymns and Spiritual Songs of Dr. Isaac Watts, published in various colonial editions beginning in the early 1700s, was frequently used as a way of "converting" African Americans to more edifying examples of Western music.³⁰

Remnants of these sufferings are commonly seen in the blues repertoire – Louis Armstrong's performance of "St. Louis Blues" with Bessie Smith clearly distinguishes a different aesthetic than other jazz standards, especially given the influence of Tin Pan Alley seen in blues songwriters including W.C. Handy.³¹

Conclusion

Given the nature of music in the United States as a response tool, especially to war and political activism,³² it is no surprise that jazz is representative of these responses from African Americans. Issues like segregation can be seen even in the performance of music, as white and black musicians were long unallowed to perform publicly together,³³ and many black artists were exploited by whites in the industry.³⁴ Though jazz grew out of distinctly African American sensibility and the aftermath of slavery, the genre not only revolutionized the popular music industry³⁵ but provides us with preservations of history for us to reflect upon and learn from.

Notes

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